

Hardware-Aware $SE(3)$ Control Barrier Functions

for Counter-UAS Interceptors with Directed Energy Payloads

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Motivation: The High-Gain Pointing Problem

Counter-UAS directed energy payloads (RF jammers, HPM)

- Reusable and non-kinetic: neutralize rogue drones without using explosives.
- Battery-limited drones need a tight beam, maximizing antenna gain and effectiveness.

Beam Φ_{\max}	Gain vs. 60°	Power saved
23°	+8.3 dB	6.8 \times
15°	+12.0 dB	16 \times

Why existing approaches fail:

- **Mechanical gimbals:** heavy, complex, and slow. Impractical on small UAVs.
- **Widen the FoV:** simply widening the beam kills the gain advantage entirely.
- **Body-fixed payload:** normal flight maneuvers will naturally violate the FoV.

Pursuit maneuvers rotate the payload
off-target mid-flight.

This paper

A **formal $SE(3)$ safety filter** that **guarantees** the boresight stays inside the FoV cone. No gimbal. No gain sacrifice.

The State Space: $SO(3)$ and $SE(3)$

$SO(3)$: rotations only

The space of all 3D rotations:

$$SO(3) = \{ \mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3} \mid \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{R} = \mathbf{I}, \det \mathbf{R} = +1 \}$$

Each \mathbf{R} rotates vectors from the body frame \mathcal{B} to the world frame \mathcal{W} .

$SE(3)$: rotations + translations

$$SE(3) \ni (\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{p}), \quad \mathbf{R} \in SO(3), \quad \mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$$

The drone's full state lives on $SE(3)$: its position **and** orientation together.

- \mathbf{p} drone position
- \mathbf{p}_T target position
- \mathbf{v}_B boresight (body frame)
- $\mathbf{R}\mathbf{v}_B$ boresight (world frame)
- $\hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{p})$ LOS unit vector to target
- ϕ pointing angle error

Working on $SE(3)$ uses the **exact** kinematics $\dot{\mathbf{R}} = \mathbf{R}\hat{\boldsymbol{\Omega}}$. No singularities, no approximations.

SE(3) Safety Function: Keeping the Boresight on Target

Objective: keep boresight $\mathbf{R}\mathbf{v}_B$ within Φ_{\max} of the LOS $\hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{p})$.

Define the **safety function**:

$$h(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{p}) \triangleq \underbrace{\mathbf{v}_B^T \mathbf{R}^T \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{p})}_{\cos(\text{pointing angle})} - \cos \Phi_{\max}$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{p}) = \frac{\mathbf{p}_T - \mathbf{p}}{\|\mathbf{p}_T - \mathbf{p}\|}$ is the LOS unit vector.

Safe set: $\mathcal{S} = \{(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{p}) : h \geq 0\}$: beam on target.

Why not a standard CBF?

Torques $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ change angular rate $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$, which changes attitude \mathbf{R} , which moves h : control is **two steps** away from h , so \dot{h} contains no control input.

Standard CBF needs control in \dot{h} . We have it only in $\ddot{h} \Rightarrow$ use **Exponential CBF (ECBF)**.

From Safety Function to Safety Filter

ECBF condition: enforce $h(t) \geq 0$ for all time:

We constrain h and its rate of change, ensuring h stays non-negative:

$$\ddot{h} \geq -c_1 \dot{h} - c_2 h - \delta$$

Choosing c_1, c_2 guarantees $h(t) \geq 0$ **forever**. Slack $\delta \geq 0$ handles takeoff transients.

Differentiating h twice along the $SE(3)$ dynamics:

$$\ddot{h} = \underbrace{L_f^2 h}_{\text{drift}} + \underbrace{L_{g_f} L_f h \cdot f}_{\text{thrust}} + \underbrace{L_{g_\tau} L_f h \cdot \tau}_{\text{torques}}$$

Every term derived in closed form. No numerical differentiation needed.

The result: one linear safety row in the QP:

$$L_{g_f} L_f h \cdot f + L_{g_\tau} L_f h \cdot \tau \geq -L_f^2 h - c_1 \dot{h} - c_2 h - \delta$$

Key structural properties

- Both τ and f appear **linearly** in \ddot{h} : torques via attitude, thrust via LOS translation. One affine constraint row, solved in microseconds.

Nguyen & Sreenath, ACC 2016.

Two-Layer Control Architecture

Lee Geometric Controller (Performance Layer)

[Lee et al., CDC 2010]

A geometric controller on $SE(3)$ for aggressive trajectory tracking. Computes nominal inputs f_{nom} and τ_{nom} to purely minimize tracking error.

Completely unaware of the pointing constraint. Pursues waypoints with no knowledge of antenna alignment.

CBF Safety Filter (This Work)

Intercepts \mathbf{u}_{nom} at every step and finds the **closest safe command** via a small QP enforcing the pointing constraint.

If \mathbf{u}_{nom} is already safe, it passes through unchanged. Zero overhead when the beam is on target.

Lee never sees the safety constraint.

The CBF uses \mathbf{p}_T and current \mathbf{p} to evaluate h at every step.

The Safety Filter QP

At each step, find the **closest safe command** to the nominal input:

$$\min_{\tilde{\mathbf{u}}} \frac{1}{2} \|\tilde{\mathbf{u}} - \mathbf{u}_{\text{nom}}\|^2 \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{A}\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \leq \mathbf{b}$$

$\tilde{\mathbf{u}} = [f, \tau_x, \tau_y, \tau_z, \delta]^T \in \mathbb{R}^5$: the 4 control inputs plus the slack.

10 constraints in $\mathbf{A}\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \leq \mathbf{b}$:

- ECBF safety condition (1 row)
- Thrust limits $f_{\min} \leq f \leq f_{\max}$ (2 rows)
- Torque limits $|\tau_i| \leq \tau_{\max}$ (6 rows)
- Slack non-negativity $\delta \geq 0$ (1 row)

What the QP guarantees

Only **1 row** comes from the CBF: the ECBF safety condition. The other 9 enforce standard actuator limits. Together they render $\mathcal{S} = \{h \geq 0\}$ forward-invariant.

The filter only activates when needed. If \mathbf{u}_{nom} is already safe, it passes through unchanged. It intervenes only when the beam is at risk of leaving the FoV cone.

Solving the QP in Real Time: ADMM

ADMM (Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers)

A first-order algorithm that splits the QP into subproblems each solved in closed form. Three steps, repeated until convergence:

Why ADMM over standard solvers?

- **Fixed per-iteration cost:** two back-solves on a fixed 5×5 matrix. Cost never changes with flight condition.
- **Warm-starting:** reuses the previous solution, converging in a few iterations on average. Interior-point methods cannot do this.
- **Graceful infeasibility:** when constraints are temporarily infeasible (e.g. at takeoff), ADMM finds the best approximate solution via slack δ . Interior-point methods diverge.

Scenario

A 1.0 kg interceptor pursues a moving target along a **four-waypoint closed-loop trajectory** (25 s). Yaw tracks the next waypoint continuously, so the drone is always turning. This is the hardest case for the CBF: every yaw maneuver tends to sweep the boresight away from the target.

FoV half-angle Φ_{\max} is swept from 25° down to 15° to test how tightly the constraint can be tightened without losing safety or agility.

Methods

- **Unfiltered**: Lee controller only. No awareness of the pointing constraint. Benchmark floor.
- **Pitch clamp**: clips pitch to Φ_{\max} . Blind to roll and yaw, so the beam still exits the FoV cone.
- **MPC-CBF**: receding-horizon QP with CBF. Open-loop predictions are overly conservative: the drone clips its trajectory and misses waypoints.
- **ADMM-CBF (ours)**: CBF filter at 250 Hz. Finds the closest safe command at each step with no future-horizon pessimism.

SE(3) Simulation: 4-Way Comparison ($\Phi_{\max} = 25^\circ$)

Method	min h	Viol. (%)
Unfiltered	-0.345	12.3
Pitch clamp	-0.344	12.4
ADMM-CBF	-0.001*	0.0
MPC-CBF	+0.084	0.0

*Within integration tolerance.

- **Pitch clamp**: 12.4% vs. 12.3%, roll/yaw coupling renders it useless
- **MPC-CBF**: open-loop pessimism \Rightarrow max pitch 5.1° , misses waypoints
- **ADMM-CBF**: zero violations, all waypoints reached, pitch 18.8°

Beam Tightening: Zero Violations, 12.0 dB Recovery

Φ_{max}	Viol. (%)	Gain (dB)
25°	0.0	+7.6
23°	0.0	+8.3
20°	0.0	+9.5
15°	0.0	+12.0

Zero violations across the entire beam-tightening range.

Tightening $25^\circ \rightarrow 15^\circ$ recovers **4.4 dB** more gain (16 \times power reduction) at no safety cost.

Slack $\delta > 0$ only during takeoff transients, otherwise $\delta \approx 0$.

SITL Validation Architecture

Three ROS 2 nodes:

- **Mission node:** Lee $SE(3)$ controller (50 Hz)
- **CBF node:** ADMM safety filter (250 Hz)
- **Custom physics:** 6-DOF rigid-body integrator (250 Hz)

Control at **body-rate level**: bypasses PX4 attitude controller, highest bandwidth on the stack.

PX4-compatible uORB topics for real deployment compatibility.

Custom 6-DOF SITL: Closed-Loop Validation

x500 airframe, 60 s, 250 Hz, ROS 2 +
PX4-compatible QoS

	Unfiltered	ADMM-CBF
min h	-0.019	+0.040
Viol. (%)	0.3	0.0
Max pitch	28.1°	20.0°
Max roll	19.2°	24.0°

- Zero violations over 14,500 armed steps
- CBF redirects pitch to roll: lower pitch (LOS-safe), higher roll (does not violate)
- Mean step: **347 μ s** at 250 Hz

Demo: ADMM-CBF vs. Unfiltered Baseline

ADMM-CBF: FoV cone stays green throughout

Unfiltered: cone flares red on violation

Conclusions

- Formulated boresight safety as a **barrier function on $SE(3)$** : pointing angle $\phi = \angle(\mathbf{R}\mathbf{v}_B, \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{p}))$ as the constraint.
- Designed an **ECBF** enforcing alignment on the full rigid-body state (\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{p}) . Exact geometry: no singularities, no small-angle approximations.
- QP safety filter runs in **347 μs** (Python, 250 Hz). Drop-in ready for embedded C++ deployment.

Key result

$SE(3)$ ECBF: **zero pointing violations** at $\Phi_{\max} = 15^\circ$ vs. **12.4%** for the baseline pitch clamp. Narrowing to 15° recovers **+12 dB** gain (**16 \times** less transmit power).

Future work:

- HITL validation and real flight, moving-target tracking with replanning, and robust CBF under state-estimation noise.
- Generalization to UAV-to-BS directional communication (e.g., mmWave beamforming), where the same antenna pointing constraint applies.

Thank you. Questions?

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